

Chemical Components of *Dodonaea viscosa* Stems

HEMLATA and S. B. KALIDHAR*

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004

Manuscript received 20 October 1992, revised 22 April 1993, accepted 28 April

Dodonaea viscosa Jacq., popularly known as 'aliar' and 'vilayati mehndi' in India, is the most abundant species of this genus of the Sapindaceae family. A number of terpenoids¹ and flavonoids² have been reported from different parts of this plant. However, there is no report of extensive chemical investigations on the stems of *D. viscosa* for their phenolic constituents. We, therefore, examined the stems of *D. viscosa* for their phenolic components.

The stems (5 kg) of *D. viscosa* were extracted with hot methanol and the extractives were subjected to silica gel column chromatography. Elutions with (i) petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1), (ii) benzene, (iii) benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1), (iv) benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) and (v) benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1), afforded respectively 4-hydroxy-3,5-diprenyl-benzaldehyde (**1**; 12 mg); β -sitosterol (**2**; 70 mg) and stearic acid (**3**; 12 mg); syringic acid (**4**; 10 mg); fraxetin (**5**; 8 mg), cleomiscosin A (**6**; 30 mg) and cleomiscosin C (**7**; 25 mg); and β -sitosterol- β -glucoside (**8**; 120 mg). The structures arrived at are based upon spectral and other data and direct comparison.

Compound 1 : It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless crystals, m.p. 118°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 150, 1 650, 1 575, 1 280, 1 120, 965, 875, 765 and 710 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 10.00 (1H, s, CHO), 7.71 (2H, s, H-2, H-6), 6.13 (1H, br s, OH), 5.43 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $2 \times \text{C}=\text{CHCH}_2$), 3.46 (4H, d, J 7 Hz, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_2$) and 1.82 (12H, s, four aliphatic methyls); m/z (rel. int.) 258 (M^+ , 68.4), 229 (18.0), 203 (60.5), 187 (73.3) and 173 (47.7). It was characterised

as 4-hydroxy-3,5-bis(3-methyl-2-butenyl)benzaldehyde (**1**) reported earlier from *Senecio* species³.

Compound 5 : It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene as colourless crystals, m.p. 225°; gave dark green colour with alcoholic ferric chlorides; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 258 and 339 nm; λ_{\max} (MeOH-NaOH) 270 and 397 nm; δ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-d}_6$) 9.00 (2H, br s, $2 \times \text{OH}$), 7.80 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4), 6.67 (1H, s, H-5), 6.23 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 3.97 (3H, s, OMe). It was identified as fraxetin (**5**)⁴.

Compound 7 : It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene as colourless crystals, m.p. 220°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 360, 1 665, 1 595, 1 550, 1 200, 1 100, 1 040, 960, 805 and 700 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. int.) 416 (M^+ , 4.8), 385 (17.4), 210 (100), 208 (85.5), 193 (30.9), 182 (32.6), 181 (17.1), 180 (36.5), 167 (51.6) and 154 (17.8); the diacetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$) δ (CDCl_3) 7.73 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4), 6.73 (2H, s, H-2', H-6'), 6.63 (1H, s, H-5), 6.38 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 5.01 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, ArCH-O-), 4.56-4.17 (3H, m, OCHCH_2OAc), 3.90 (3H, s, OMe-6), 3.84 (6H, s, OMe-3', OMe-5'), 2.33 (3H, s, OAc-4'), 2.06 (3H, s, $\text{CH-CH}_2\text{OCOCH}_3$); δ (C_6D_6) 6.64 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4), 6.34 (2H, s, H-2', H-6'), 5.96 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 5.94 (1H, s, H-5), 4.49 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, Ar-CH-O-), 4.20-3.92 (3H, m, $-\text{O-CHCH}_2\text{OAc}$), 3.35 (3H, s, OMe-6), 3.23 (6H, s, OMe-3', OMe-5'), 1.95 (3H, s, OAc-4') and 1.58 (3H, s, $\text{CHCH}_2\text{OCOCH}_3$). It was characterised as cleomiscosin C (**7**) reported earlier from *Cleome viscosa*⁵.

References

1. H. Y. HSU, Y. P. CHEN and H. KAKISAWA, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, **10**, 2813; K. SACHDEV and D. K. KULSHRESHTHA, *Planta Med.*, 1984, **50**, 448; M. Z. DIMBI, M. KAPUNDU, E. DARIMONT, R. WARIN, C. DELAUDE and R. HULS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1985, **94**, 141; V. U. AHMAD, I. FATIMA and A. FATIMA, *Fitoterpia*, 1987, **58**, 361.
2. A. G. R. NAIR and S. S. SUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 639; D. L. DREYER, *Rev. Latinoam. Quim.*, 1978, **9**, 97; K. SACHDEV and D. K. KULSHRESHTHA, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 1253; K. SACHDEV and D. K. KULSHRESHTHA, *Phytochemistry*, 1986, **25**, 1967.
3. F. BOHLMANN, C. ZDERO, J. JAKUPOVIC, L. N. MISRA, S. BANERJEE, P. SINGH, R. N. BARAUH, M. A. METWALLY, G. SCHMEDAHIRSCHMANN, L. P. D. VINCENT, R. M. KING and H. ROBINSON, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 1249.
4. V. K. AHLUWALIA, V. N. GUPTA, C. L. RUSTAGI and T. R. SESHADRI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. B*, 1960, **19**, 345.
5. A. B. RAY, S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, S. KUMAR, C. KANNO, Y. KISO and H. HIKINO, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 209.